
Experimental evaluation of the DFINITY Internet Computer

Master of Science in Computer Science

Under the supervision of:

Prof. Dr. Hans-Georg Fill

Submitted by:

Alexandru Filipescu

(Matriculation Number: 21-113-998)

Digitalization and Information Systems Group
Department of Informatics
University of Fribourg

Fribourg, June 16, 2023

Abstract

The motivation to create this master thesis comes from the desire to find out and analyse how the basic processes of the Internet Computer work. The various challenges I want to answer are about: How can a sample application be implemented and evaluated on DFINITY? How is the Internet Computer architecture structured and its processes? And what are the approaches for running decentralized applications using blockchain technologies in general, and how can they be classified. In the approach that I took, I used the design science research method whereby I analysed many of the processes of the Internet Computer and sketched them through UML diagrams such as: activity, sequence, state or class. As a direct result, I was able to obtain many explanatory models of the base processes that are carried out by the Internet Computer. Not only that, but also the development of a CRUD chat application with Motoko helped me to better understand the functioning of this new programming language.

List of Figures

1.1	Simplified Blockchain Architecture (Shrimali & Patel, 2022)	8
2.1	Overview of design science research (Myllymäki, 2018)	14
3.1	One single distribution server (left), and a system of CDN servers (right) (Team, 2019).	25
4.1	New artifact in the artifact pool	32
4.2	"Download next" functionality	33
4.3	How to receive an artifact?	34
4.4	Transient network problems	35
4.5	Disconnected or full queue	36
4.6	Block Making	38
4.7	Notarization	39
4.8	Random Beacon	40
4.9	Notarization with Block Maker Ranking	41
4.10	Finalization process	42
4.11	High level intuition of deterministic execution cycle	44
4.12	How do messages reach other subnets	45
4.13	Stream transfer protocol	46
4.14	Scheduling canisters on the Internet Computer	48
4.15	Executing a single message	49
4.16	Subnets progress	50

4.17	Time slicing	51
4.18	Creating a DFX project on the Internet Computer	53
4.19	Deploying a DFX project locally.	55
4.20	Deploying a DFX project on-chain on the Internet Computer.	56
4.21	Deploying a DFX project on-chain on the Internet Computer with Fleek.co	57
4.22	Start/Stop a canister	58
4.23	Canister upgrade	60
4.24	Canister states	61
4.25	Canister creation	63
4.26	Submitting a node proposal	65
4.27	Voting rewards	66
4.28	Following	67
4.29	Contract execution on the blockchain	68
4.30	Concept of a chat system based on hierarchy	70
4.31	Sequence diagram of chat functionalities	71
4.32	Chat system based on hierarchy	72
4.33	Inside the Chatroom	73
4.34	DHierarchify actor class	74
4.35	The front-end of Hierarchify on-chain	75
4.36	Candid UI, the backend of Hierarchify	76
4.37	The running canister and its ID, represented by the IC Dashboard	77

Contents

1	Introduction	6
1.1	Background and motivation	6
1.1.1	The definition of a blockchain	7
1.1.2	Challenges of decentralized systems	8
1.1.3	DFINITY's decentralized network	9
1.2	Problem statement	9
1.3	Research questions	10
1.3.1	About the research questions	10
1.4	Conclusion	11
2	Research methodology	12
2.1	Approach and methods used in the research	12
2.2	Data collection and analysis techniques	13
2.3	Limits and assumptions of the evaluation	14
2.4	Conclusion	15
3	Foundations	16
3.1	Fundamentals of blockchain and smart contracts	16
3.1.1	What is blockchain?	16
3.1.2	Smart contracts	17
3.1.3	Proof of work versus proof of stake	17
3.1.4	Decentralized computing used by blockchains	20

3.2	Regarding traditional internet services	20
3.2.1	Traditional hosting	21
3.2.2	Content delivery networks	24
3.2.3	Proxy Servers	25
3.3	DFINITY's importance in blockchain	27
3.3.1	DFINITY'S consensus algorithm	27
3.4	Blockchain and the traditional internet services	27
3.5	Conclusion	27
4	Experimental Analysis of DFINITY	29
4.1	Description of the experimental setup	29
4.2	Implementation of the experimental procedures	29
4.2.1	Peer-to-peer	30
4.2.2	Consensus	37
4.2.3	Message routing	42
4.2.4	Execution	46
4.3	Experimental results analysis and interpretation	51
4.3.1	Creating a dapp project locally via dfx	53
4.3.2	Deploying a project locally	55
4.3.3	Deploying a project on-chain via CLI	56
4.3.4	Deploying a project on-chain with Fleek.co	57
4.4	Features to be mentioned	59
4.4.1	Canister lifecycle	59
4.4.2	Canister creation	62
4.4.3	Network Nervous System	64
4.4.4	Contract execution on the blockchain in its structure	67
4.4.5	What is Motoko?	68
4.4.6	Experimental results of the Hierarchify chat app	69

4.5	On-chain project	74
4.6	Conclusion	77
5	Evaluation	78
5.1	SWOT analysis of DFINITY's platform	78
5.1.1	Strenghts	79
5.1.2	Weaknesses	79
5.1.3	Opportunities	79
5.1.4	Threats	80
5.2	Suggestions for further research and development	80
5.3	Conclusion	81
6	Conclusions and Outlook	82
6.1	Thesis main findings and contributions summary	82
6.2	Implications of blockchain and related technologies	82
6.3	Applications and future research of the methodology	83
	References	84

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background and motivation

In the next chapter, I set my goal and objective to discuss issues such as: the motivation for choosing this master's thesis, explaining clearly and defining blockchain and the challenges that decentralized systems pose and also how this relates to DFINITY's decentralized network. Nevertheless, I will address the problem statement itself and explain what the research questions are and what I am addressing.

One of the main reasons for choosing this topic for my master thesis, is because I was inspired by the proposal of Prof. Hans-Georg Fill. As such, I would like to develop and deepen the topic of "Experimental evaluation of the DFINITY Internet Computer". The foundation of this master thesis will be based on: testing, analysing and evaluating the "internet computer". As proposed, the main objective of the thesis is to examine the key operations of the Internet Computer and represented them graphically. I have done it by using UML diagrams for activities, sequences, states, and classes. As a result, I was able to acquire several explanatory models of the fundamental operations performed by the Internet Computer.

Another goal is to find out the different qualities and weaknesses, that the internet computer has compared to cloud services. At the same time I intend to test within the possibilities of the SDK offered by the DFINITY team. Various benefits that the "Internet Computer mainnet" attributes to itself such as: new internet infrastructure without the need for a trusted central system, censorship resistant web apps (Web 3.0) and border-less availability are some of the features that are proposed and marketed. I want to test whether the DFINITY team achieves what it aims out to do, or at least partially achieves it.

I'm also interested in exploring third-party software tools and testing the techniques and methods that they propose. One such software that can be used adjacent to the Internet Computer is "Fleek.co", it propagates information and static web pages to the internet computer network. More can be read here: "<https://fleek.co/internet-computer-hosting/>". It is

different from the standard method of uploading web pages through the Internet Computer (which uses the command line and various specific commands). The method used by the "Fleek.co" web-app differs from the original technique because it uses a GUI interface and makes use of repositories (e.g. GitHub, GitLab, Bitbucket), on which static pages are uploaded, then build settings are added and in the last step the web page/application can be launched.

A very important point I want to make is the differentiation between front-end and back-end canisters. They have different roles, the front-end one has the main role of connecting with end users using a web browser. The back-end canisters (data bucket canister) wait to receive cross-canister query call request from the front-end canisters, and they will reply with the requested data.

Another reason for the inspiration for choosing this thesis subject, comes from the curiosity to find, learn, and understand more about an alternative way to request resources that are translated to web pages via the browser, other than the traditional web hosting. On the traditional web hosting, files that relate to a website are stored on a server which serves the requested information and resources (via the URL) to the client. As mentioned in the following paper (Taivalaari, Mikkonen, Ingalls, & Palacz, 2008) Web-based applications have major benefits: no installation or upgrades needed, instant worldwide deployment, the ability to own the users' data. There's more to hosting than just space and bandwidth. The site is on a server which is just a big computer. When people visit your site, the server has to do some thinking to deliver web pages the visitors want to view (Pollock, 2013). Another good definition of how servers work: A client is your own computer and the software that sits on it, such as a Web browser or a piece of email software (Gralla, 1998). Clients request information from servers, which do the heavy-duty processing and then send the information back to the client, which displays the information (Gralla, 1998).

In order to understand correctly the motivation for my proposal, first, we will have to understand an important concept which is topical, namely: Blockchain.

1.1.1 The definition of a blockchain

What is blockchain?

A blockchain is (Natarajan, Krause, & Gradstein, 2017) a particular type of data structure used in some distributed ledgers which stores and transmits data in packages called blocks that are connected to each other in a digital chain. Blockchains employ cryptographic and algorithmic methods to record and synchronize data across a network in an immutable manner.

The technology known as the blockchain was first revealed by Satoshi Nakamoto in his paper Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System which laid out the mathematical foundation for the bitcoin cryptocurrency. Blockchain technology is not only at the foundation of all cryptocurrencies, but it has found wide application in the more traditional financial

industry. It also opened the door to new applications such as smart contracts (Di Piero, 2017). As we can see, this technology is relatively new and promises a new way of dealing with virtual currencies. This technology was initially aimed towards the financial industry, but with the passing of time, it has proven to have many more applications. Blockchain technology (Vyawahare, 2021) and distributed ledgers are attracting massive attention and trigger multiple projects in different industries. However, the financial industry is seen as a primary user of the blockchain concept (Nofer, Gomber, Hinz, & Schiereck, 2017). Another good use case of this technology is to keep track of multiple transactions among different entities. Intermediation is today's dominating solution for verifying ownership of assets and transaction processing. However, this is not only time-consuming and costly, but also bears a credit risk in case an intermediary fails (Nofer et al., 2017). In the figure labelled "Simplified Blockchain Architecture" we can see a good representation of how the blocks are connected to each other.

Figure 1.1: Simplified Blockchain Architecture (Shrimali & Patel, 2022)

It is necessary to understand that blockchain uses decentralized computing (Kelly, 2020) (performed by a multitude of separate entities), and comes as an alternative to centralized computing power (performed by a single entity). While a distributed system (Wu, 1998) can loosely be defined as a collection of independent computers that appears to its users as a single coherent system, a basic definition of a decentralized system requires these independent computers to be controlled by multiple authorities, such that no authority is fully trusted by all. In other words, authorities or operators controlling computers of a system are assumed to be potentially malicious (Vukolic et al., 2021).

1.1.2 Challenges of decentralized systems

Since in a decentralized network we are interacting with independent participants, it is challenging to keep track of and supervise each one of them. Moreover, decentralized

networks (aws.amazon, 2023) strive to reduce the level of trust that participants must place in one another, and deter their ability to exert authority or control over one another in ways that degrade the functionality of the network. It can also be noted (El Faqir, Arroyo, & Hassan, 2020) that governance under blockchain is challenging per se, since it is difficult to steer a decentralized community and promote its development without sacrificing decentralisation.

A proposal that plans to solve many of today's challenges regarding distributed computing, comes from the DFINITY Foundation, they suggest a supercomputer called the "internet computer", I will go into more detail in the chapter number 4.

1.1.3 DFINITY's decentralized network

DFINITY (Hanke, Movahedi, & Williams, 2018) is a decentralized network design whose protocols generate a reliable virtual blockchain computer running on top of a peer-to-peer network upon which software can be installed and can operate in the tamper-proof mode of smart contracts, the goal is for the virtual computer to analyse computations quickly, to provide predictable performance, and for computational and storage capacity to scale up without bounds as demand for its services increases. (Hanke et al., 2018).

1.2 Problem statement

The main objective of this master thesis, is to verify and test the various qualities that "Internet Computer" has. Some of the strengths that the DFINITY team promises are: trustless and censorship-resistant internet infrastructure. Another interesting feature, and one I want to look into, is the ability to launch web pages that automatically hold the SSL certificate, without the need for manual generation of a certificate.

At the same time, I want to analyse and compare the differences between launching a web page using the techniques (CLI) provided by the DFINITY team, using the command line for all the necessary procedures.

I also want to test the option of launching a web page using an external service, which uses a graphical user interface (GUI). This service is offered by the company "https://fleek.co". The result that should emerge is expected to be identical, but the number of steps and their difficulty is expected to be different. I propose to compare the two techniques and highlight the two techniques, depending on the time left, these tests can even be extended to web applications, not just web pages.

1.3 Research questions

The purpose of this section is to list some of the questions that have arisen throughout this master thesis, and it will be motivated why they are interesting.

1.3.1 About the research questions

Research questions are questions that a project aims to answer. These questions (Andrews, 2003) address a problem or challenge, which through interpretation of the data and analysis will be answered in the final conclusion of a study. Often, in such studies the research question is formulated in such a way (Andrews, 2003) as to emphasise various aspects such as the target outcome and the variables to be studied as well as the problems the study addresses.

A research question is dynamic (White, 2017), and from this it follows that researchers can change and improve their research questions as they continue to document and inform themselves from the various sources around them until they develop a favourable framework around them. Large research (White, 2017) projects focus on answering multiple questions, while regular ones strive to answer a single question.

Also, as mentioned before and as the following document shows (Thabane, Thomas, Ye, & Paul, 2009): A research question needs to be well-defined, purposeful and meaningful. There is even a table called the FINER (Mohanani, Parameswaran, et al., 2022) criteria which suggests that a scientific question should have several qualities such as: feasibility, novelty, be ethical and relevant.

For experienced researchers, this is a familiar and straightforward procedure, but for beginners it is recommended to have a mentor. The research questions in my thesis were suggested and proposed by Prof. Hans Georg Fill.

An example to narrow down the concept of what research can be seen in the following list:

1. Subject
2. Working knowledge about the topic (topic)
3. Working questions
4. Research questions (after an evaluation)

One way to deploy decentralized web applications (Alabdulwahhab, 2018) is to build them using a JavaScript framework such as Web3.js combined with Metamask (accessible via a web browser extension) that plays the role of a digital wallet and which is the intermediary between the blockchain network and the decentralized web application itself. As we can clearly see, many components of the previously mentioned decentralized web application

are heterogeneous and must be interconnected between them in order for the application to work. Therefore, the following questions will be answered:

- What are approaches for running decentralized apps using blockchain technologies in general, and how can they be classified?
- What are the architecture and processes of DFINITY?
- How can a sample application on DFINITY be implemented and evaluated?

1.4 Conclusion

In order to conclude this chapter, It needed to be mentioned that the main objective was to introduce my master's thesis regarding the experimental evaluation of DFINITY's Internet Computer. This is possible by aiming to explore the qualities of the Internet Computer, compare it to cloud services, test third-party tools like "Fleek.co" and examine the differentiation between front-end and back-end canisters. The thesis also provides an overview of blockchain technology and the challenges of decentralized systems. Another goal is to focus on verifying the Internet Computer's features, this will be done by addressing research questions related to deployment approaches and implementation of DFINITY's Internet Computer.

Chapter 2

Research methodology

2.1 Approach and methods used in the research

In the current chapter I want to discuss the reasons but also the qualities that made me choose Design Science Research as a technique to approach various research problems. I will explain the data collection and analysis techniques but also the limitations and assumptions of the evaluation my project might go through.

I chose DSR (Design Science Research) after considering various methodologies. Design science (A. Hevner, Chatterjee, Hevner, & Chatterjee, 2010) creates and evaluates IT artefacts to solve organizational problems. These artefacts (Andrews, 2003) can take the form of structured representations such as software or formal logic.

Design science (A. Hevner et al., 2010) creates technological artefacts that have an impact on people and organizations. It aims to solve problems but sometimes oversimplifies the people and organizational contexts in which these artefacts need to operate (Baskerville, Pries-Heje, & Venable, 2009).

DSR develops new technologies to solve (Dresch et al., 2015) problems, often of a sociotechnical nature. However, DSR faces challenges in understanding problems, identifying suitable solutions, and effectively evaluating innovative solutions.

These reasons influenced my choice of research methodology as the backbone of my project. Design science research starts by identifying and representing opportunities and problems in a real-world application context. It takes a pragmatic (A. R. Hevner, 2007) approach, emphasizing (A. R. Hevner, 2007) relevance and making a clear contribution to the application environment.

Another reason (Venable, Pries-Heje, & Baskerville, 2016) for choosing DSR is its continuous and flexible evolution, allowing for iterative progress until objectives are achieved. Evaluation is tightly (Dresch et al., 2015) coupled with the design process, influencing designer thinking and enabling rapid cycles of building and evaluation. Design science research

is problem-focused (March & Storey, 2008), initially focusing on constructing sufficient actions to achieve goals in a new problem area.

As part of the design science process, It's important to mention the six different activities that DSR aims to satisfy (Peppers, Tuunanen, Rothenberger, & Chatterjee, 2007):

Problem identification and motivation: Define the specific research problem and justify the value of a solution.

Definition of the objectives for a solution: Infer the objectives of a solution from the problem definition and knowledge of what is possible and feasible.

Design and development: Create the artifact. Conceptually, a design research artifact can be any designed object in which a research contribution is embedded in the design.

Demonstration: Demonstrate the use of the artifact to solve one or more instances of the problem. This could involve its use in experimentation, simulation, case study, proof, or other appropriate activity. Resources required for the demonstration include effective knowledge of how to use the artifact to solve the problem.

In order to use the methodology activities successfully, it is necessary to combine them with my project in such a way that they fit.

Problem identification and motivation: I am challenged with testing the internet computer efficiently. Initially, I plan to implement experimental procedures. Another option is to develop a web application and test its compatibility on regular servers and the blockchain-based servers provided by the DFINITY team.

Definition of the objectives for a solution: Obtain experimental results by modeling the processes and procedures of the Internet Computer. Secondary objectives, to be discussed with the coordinator, include testing and comparing application performance, analysing hosting costs, server utilization limits, content delivery network comparisons, and assessing uptime and availability.

Design and development: The primary plan is to use UML diagrams to simplify the representation of essential processes. Additionally, a hierarchical chat portal will be designed, allowing entry into different rooms using codes and names, with the room creator acting as the owner.

Demonstration: Instructions will be created to guide users in achieving the desired results. The portal will include screenshots and code explanations to assist users.

2.2 Data collection and analysis techniques

The techniques (Dresch et al., 2015) used to collect data for subsequent analysis are as follows.

Evaluation: Observe and measure how well the artifact supports a solution to the problem.

Communication: Communicate the problem’s significance, the artifact’s utility, novelty, design rigour, and effectiveness.

And if we are talking specifically about my project, this is the concrete way I will apply the techniques:

Evaluation: Based on the results of comparing centralized and decentralized technologies, we will draw valid conclusions for the evaluation, which can be either conclusive or inconclusive.

Communication: I undertake to report all advantages, disadvantages, conclusions and results obtained from the various tests carried out, in writing and verbally to my supervisor.

Figure 2.1: Overview of design science research (Myllymäki, 2018)

2.3 Limits and assumptions of the evaluation

My project may encounter a challenge regarding the implementation of a CRUD application. This challenge arises from the absence of databases (such as SQL or NoSQL) specifically designed for the Internet Computer. This would offer programmers an accessible and user-friendly suite of tools. As a result, programmers are required to rely on conventional data structures in order to carry out CRUD operations.

Programmers and independent communities have developed alternative solutions like "Sudograph" (<https://github.com/sudograph/sudograph>), which aim to emulate GraphQL.

While there are numerous similar projects available, I have not yet come across one that is officially developed or maintained by the Internet Computer team.

2.4 Conclusion

To conclude this chapter, it has to be mentioned that one of the main reason for choosing DSR as the research methodology for the thesis, is because it creates and evaluates IT artefacts to solve organizational problems. Important and needed activities for the evaluation are: Problem identification and motivation, definition of the objectives for a solution, design, development and demonstration. DSR was the best fit for the Master's thesis in accordance with the research questions posed and compared to other existing research methodologies. Another reason for choosing DSR is related to data collection and analysis techniques such as evaluation and communication. Limits and assumptions of the evaluation led me to mention challenges that may arise in the development of the CRUD application due to the lack of a database management system.

Chapter 3

Foundations

3.1 Fundamentals of blockchain and smart contracts

As far as this chapter is concerned, the main objectives are to focus specifically on explaining certain features of blockchain such as Smart contracts, Proof of Work and Proof of Stake. Then I will make a transition to the traditional web technologies (web hosting types, CDNs, proxy servers) that are most common, and I will highlight how they work. Towards the end, with all of the above I will be able to clarify the link and connection between the novelty of the Internet Computer and traditional web technologies.

In this section I will provide details about what a blockchain is, and compare different ways of operating them such as: proof of work or proof of stake. I will also highlight some clear examples of this technology.

3.1.1 What is blockchain?

Blockchain (Monrat, Schelén, & Andersson, 2019) is the underlying technology of a number of digital cryptocurrencies. Blockchain (Nofer et al., 2017) is a chain of blocks that store information with digital signatures in a decentralized and distributed network. The features of blockchain, including (Nofer et al., 2017) decentralization, immutability, transparency and auditability, make transactions more secure and tamperproof. The technology known as the blockchain was first (Nakamoto, 2008) revealed by Satoshi Nakamoto in his paper Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System which laid out the mathematical foundation for the bitcoin cryptocurrency. Blockchain technology is not only at the foundation (Di Pierro, 2017) of all cryptocurrencies, but it has found wide application in the more traditional financial industry. It also opened the door to new applications such as smart contracts (Di Pierro, 2017). As we can see, this technology is relatively new and promises a new way of dealing with virtual currencies. This technology was initially aimed towards the financial industry, but with the passage of time it has proven to have many more applications. Blockchain

technology and distributed ledgers are attracting (Monrat et al., 2019) massive attention and trigger multiple projects in different industries. However, the financial industry is seen as a primary user of the blockchain concept (Monrat et al., 2019). Another good use case of this technology is to keep track of multiple transactions among different entities. Intermediation is a solution (Nofer et al., 2017) for verifying ownership of assets and transaction processing. Intermediaries perform the careful checking of each involved party along a chain of intermediaries. However, this is not only time-consuming and costly, but also bears a credit risk in case an intermediary fails (Nofer et al., 2017).

To summarize it, a blockchain (Gupta, 2018) is a shared, immutable ledger that facilitates the process of recording transactions and tracking assets in a business network. Blockchain (Gupta, 2018) is ideal for delivering that information because it provides immediate, shared and completely transparent information stored on an immutable ledger that can be accessed only by permissioned network members.

3.1.2 Smart contracts

A smart contract (Zheng et al., 2020) is a small computer program that is perpetuated in a blockchain. With smart contracts we can build systems that can replace third parties, providing trust between 2 parties. Some very important properties that smart contracts inherit from blockchains are (Zou et al., 2019): immutability and distributivity. Immutability refers to the fact that once a smart contract has been created, it cannot be changed. Distributivity (Zou et al., 2019) refers to the property that the contract's output data is validated by everyone on the network. That is, an intruder has no possibility to appropriate some funds because other participants will stop him.

Another source states that: smart contracts (IBM, 2023) are simply programs stored on a blockchain that run when predetermined conditions are met. They typically are used to automate the execution of an agreement so that all participants can be immediately certain of the outcome, without any intermediaries involvement or time loss. They can also automate a workflow, triggering the next action when conditions are met.

In other words, a smart contract (Gupta, 2018) is an agreement or set of rules that govern a business transaction; its stored on the blockchain and is executed automatically as part of a transaction.

3.1.3 Proof of work versus proof of stake

There are two main existing mechanisms that are used for consensus. They are useful because they are essential for cryptocurrency transactions and security. These consensus mechanisms (Zhang, Wu, & Wang, 2020) are absolutely necessary for blockchain technology, namely Poof-of-stake and Proof-of-work. Both of these, although in different ways, help us to ensure that transactions are carried out by honest users, this can be achieved by inducing

difficulties and high costs for dishonest members and encouraging and supporting honest members.

The core idea of Proof of Work (PoW) (Mingxiao, Xiaofeng, Zhe, Xiangwei, & Qijun, 2017) is to allocate the accounting rights and rewards through the hashing power competition among the nodes. Based on the information of the previous block, the different nodes calculate (Mingxiao et al., 2017) the specific solution of a mathematical problem. The first node that solves this maths problem can create the next block and get a certain amount of rewards.

Proof of Stake technology uses randomly chosen validators to make sure transactions are trustworthy and then reward them with cryptocurrency. To validate transactions, validators (Gupta, 2018) must hold a certain percentage of the networks total value. Proof of stake might provide increased protection from a malicious attack on the network by reducing incentives for attack and making it very expensive to execute attacks.

There are advantages and disadvantages to both sides (Vashchuk & Shuwar, 2018):

Proof of work pros and cons.

Pros

- Due to operating costs, the network has high security
- Decentralization and openness are prevalent qualities in the network
- It is the only mechanism that has proven to be viable on a large scale

Cons

- The amount of electricity used is extremely high
- Electronic waste generated is considerably higher compared to proof of stake
- Technology is less scalable and slower than proof of stake

Proof of stake pros and cons.

Pros

- Enables very fast and scalable transactions
- Has a much lower environmental impact
- Provides a financial reward for approving and validating blocks

Cons

- Has not been sufficiently tested to prove viable on a large scale
- Tends to appropriate centralization
- Compared to proof of work may not be as resistant to manipulation

Now that we have exposed (Mingxiao et al., 2017) some of the pros and cons, we can get an idea of the advantages and disadvantages of these techniques, for verifying and rewarding the entities that initiate the processes listed above.

To better understand both technologies, it is necessary to take each one separately and analyse (Sriman, Kumar, & Prabakaran, 2020) them. In the case of proof of work, we have the following steps:

1. Group the transactions together in a block.
2. Miners check the validity of the transactions in each block.
3. Verification is done by solving mathematical puzzles.
4. A reward is given to the first miner who solves the challenge of the block first.
5. Verified transactions are saved to the public blockchain.

Some challenges (Sriman et al., 2020) to consider is that a miner will need hardware equipment to mine. Often, miners (Sriman et al., 2020) join mining pools to offer their hashing-power and in the end (if a block is mined) divide their profits according to the work done.

In general terms (Bentov, Lee, Mizrahi, & Rosenfeld, 2014), Proof of Work based protocols give the decision-making power to entities who perform computational tasks, while proof of stake based protocols give the decision-making power to entities who hold stake in the system.

The procedures are totally different (Sriman et al., 2020) for the proof of stake technique, as shown below:

1. Transactions are grouped in a block
2. Validators will stake to be randomly selected in a certain way
3. Validators will create a new block
4. Validators will receive the fees of the transactions in a block, but they will lose part of the stake if they verify a fraudulent transaction.
5. Transactions already verified will be put into the public blockchain.

One of the risks with proof of stake is that: (Bentov et al., 2014) new kinds of centralization risks are introduced (large stakeholders may try to exhibit control over the system.

3.1.4 Decentralized computing used by blockchains

It is necessary to understand that blockchains use (Kelly, 2020) decentralized computing (performed by a multitude of separate entities), and comes as an alternative to centralized computing power (performed by a single entity). Decentralized systems are a subset of distributed systems, while a distributed system (Kelly, 2020) can loosely be defined as a collection of independent computers that appears to its users as a single coherent system, a basic definition of a decentralized system requires these independent computers to be controlled by multiple authorities, such that no authority is fully trusted (Vukolic et al., 2021) by all. In other words, authorities or operators controlling computers of a system are assumed to be potentially malicious.

A challenge that decentralized systems face, is in regard to the administration of dispersed systems (Mahmoud, 2011). Since we are interacting with independent entities, it is challenging to keep track of and supervise each one of them. Additionally, we must communicate general changes (Alabdulwahhab, 2018) to each entity offering the service, which necessitates a sophisticated technique. To distribute and install fixes in several locations at once, for instance, we require an updating strategy.

A proposal that suggests solving many of today's challenges regarding distributed computing, comes from the DFINITY Foundation, they propose a supercomputer called the "internet computer".

We can briefly define the Internet Computer (IC) as (Team et al., 2022) a new platform for executing smart contracts. Here, we use the term smart contract in a very broad sense: a general-purpose, tamperproof computer program whose execution is performed autonomously on a decentralized public network.

3.2 Regarding traditional internet services

In order to make a correct and concrete analysis of the platform created by DFINITY, it is necessary to list the technologies, techniques and working methods and practices that have been used in the past and present. This is necessary because in order to make a direct comparison, we need to know and understand the underpinnings of the technologies traditionally used. We can say that even though DFINITY aims to completely revolutionize web hosting methods and practices, some of the traditional technologies are still intertwined with the Internet Computer in direct and indirect ways. So there is still a connection between the novelty proposed by DFINITY and the traditional Internet as we know it that we will explore in the following chapters.

As we know, computer networks proved and showed their potential in the mid-1970s, but to reach their full potential (Day & Zimmermann, 1983), international standards needed to be implemented. To this end, the OSI (Open Systems Interconnection) reference model was developed, which is a model containing 7 different levels of abstraction as mentioned in the

following paper: (Day & Zimmermann, 1983).

Next, we list the different layers that make up the OSI network models:

1. Application Layer
2. Presentation Layer
3. Session Layer
4. Transport Layer
5. Network Layer
6. Data Link Layer
7. Physical Layer

Basically, this network (Zimmermann, 1980) architecture that was put into use in the mid-1980s is still used successfully today. This proves not only how robust it is, but also how widespread and popular it has become.

In my master's thesis I will mainly focus on the application layer, which has the role of communicating with end users and user applications. This is the layer that provides a direct link (Zimmermann, 1980) between users and the network, and the network can be accessed directly from this layer. Some known examples of services provided over this network are FTP (File transfer protocol), Email or web browsers.

3.2.1 Traditional hosting

Traditional hosting (Pollock, 2013) is often provided by a hosting provider that allocates space on a web server for web applications and websites to host their files and content. Files such as HTML code, CSS, JavaScript or images are available to be viewed by website visitors.

The main (Pollock, 2013) hosting methods are: reseller, VPS, shared and dedicated. The type of hosting is affected by various technical factors such as: memory offered, number of hosts, storage space or total bandwidth offered. These types of hosting differ in the technology used by the server but also in the different levels of administrative capabilities and possible modifications that they offer.

Below I will list some of the most popular types of hosting:

1. Shared web hosting
2. VPS hosting
3. Dedicated hosting

4. Reseller hosting
5. Cloud hosting

Shared web hosting

In shared hosting, the customer pays for the total amount of data (GB) they can store on a single server. Most often this solution is chosen by small and medium-sized companies, the advantage comes from the fact that the storage price is very low. These concepts are explained in more detail in this paper (Urgaonkar, Shenoy, & Roscoe, 2002).

One of the disadvantages (Urgaonkar et al., 2002) is the server's property of sharing the same resources among several users, which can result in slowing down your own website if one or more clients on the same server have a very high demand for their website resources.

VPS hosting

Virtual Private Servers (Balen, Vajak, & Salah, 2020) are those that are perceived by a customer as being dedicated servers, when in fact they serve multiple users. This is one of the reasons why it is seen as the next step after shared hosting. One of the most important differences between VPS and shared hosting is that VPS allows those who own it more flexibility (Balen et al., 2020) given the possible configurations, which comes close to dedicated hosting. This is why many organizations or small businesses opt for VPS hosting, which is similar to dedicated hosting but at a much lower cost.

Some of the resources made available by VPS hosts are for example: RAM, SSD storage, bandwidth, a snapshot (an image of the disk at a given time), weekly backups, a dedicated IP or root access.

Dedicated hosting

Dedicated hosting (Pollock, 2013) refers to the service that offers entire servers for rent, this hosting solution is favoured when the web hosting solution no longer has the necessary processing capacity to handle requests, or when more control is needed. For these reasons, the costs with this type of hosting are higher compared to VPS hosting or shared hosting.

Often (Balen et al., 2020) a dedicated server is purchased not just to improve the performance of a website, there are many more resources and tools available that are made available by the equipment where the server is hosted.

Basically, the dedicated server (Molnar & Schechter, 2010) offers a proprietary server maintenance solution and administration tools that help you check the security of the system and take full control of the server. Because of this, a certain degree of technical expertise is required to administer and maintain this type of server.

Reseller hosting

Reseller hosting (Anderson & Bedre-Defolie, 2022) stands out for the simple fact that it makes its resources available for an entity to rent its services to customers for a fee. So the entity acting as a reseller (Anderson & Bedre-Defolie, 2022) can offer various resources such as RAM, CPU, bandwidth or storage space, depending on the plan chosen and the total resources it needs. This form of hosting is most popular among web agencies or web development agencies who want to become web resource providers themselves.

Cloud hosting

Cloud hosting offers many advantages that traditional hosting cannot. This results from the fact that companies offering cloud hosting (Comellas, Presa, & Fernández, 2010) can deliver resources to their customers according to their needs at the time. So instead of paying a fixed/standard amount for certain resources offered by a server, customers pay a dynamic amount based on the total resources used.

In the case of cloud hosting, multiple servers that are clustered take over and distribute their user request. The way cloud servers work (Comellas et al., 2010) and the architecture of cloud servers is that applications and information are hosted on servers that are mirrored multiple times, so that by using this technique even if a server goes down there will be no data that is lost.

Due to the redundancy properties offered by this form of hosting, cloud hosting is much more flexible (Molnar & Schechter, 2010) and resilient, as the technical problems and difficulties a server will encounter will not necessarily be reflected in the functionality of the website or web application.

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) is offered by cloud hosting companies, they take care of the maintenance and upkeep of server clusters and the customer pays according to their needs.

Customers don't have to pay extra (Molnar & Schechter, 2010) for resources they don't use, and IT departments don't have to worry about or invest in the space and maintenance that would be required for physical, in-house servers. In addition to adding the necessary resources, it is also possible to reduce them as needed, this can be done automatically, this technique offers versatility and also reduces the costs. More can be read found in the following paper: (Comellas et al., 2010).

Some of the most popular cloud providers are:

1. Amazon AWS Web Services This is the largest cloud service provider in existence, as of 2014 they had coverage (Mathew & Varia, 2014) in 11 regions around the world, and as of right now (15/11/2022) they have currently 28 regions. Also, AWS owns 30% of the global share regarding cloud services.

2. Microsoft Azure It is the technology promoted by Microsoft, with strengths in PaaS (Platform as a service), IaaS (infrastructure as a service), SaaS (software as a service) and serverless solutions.
3. Google Cloud Platform It uses the same set of technologies that power the architecture behind YouTube or the Google.com search engine.

3.2.2 Content delivery networks

A content delivery system (CDN) is a group of servers that are geographically distributed in various locations and are responsible for delivering web content to those who request it, all the stated ideas are also mentioned in the following paper (Peng, 2004a).

A CDN (Papagianni, Leivadeas, & Papavassiliou, 2013) is designed to deliver information to customers at very high speeds. This information can be images, videos, JavaScript files, stylesheets or HTML pages. The popularity of CDNs is driven by big market players such as Amazon, Netflix and Facebook.

Another big advantage of CDNs is that they can protect web pages from DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) attacks.

One important subject (Papagianni et al., 2013) worth mentioning and keeping in mind is that a CDN is not a proper web hosting service or a replacement for it, as it only caches content in nodes geographically close to users. By using caching, the bandwidth used is reduced, which will result in preventing system outages and improving security.

There are a number of benefits (Peng, 2004b) to using a CDN, and it depends on the need and needs of those who want to implement it:

1. Reduce bandwidth costs: These (Peng, 2004b) are some of the main costs a web host has to pay for web pages or websites. Through well-thought-out optimizations, it is possible to reduce the number of requests that the main server receives, through this technique, costs are reduced.
2. Website security is enhanced: A well-designed CDN can protect an ordinary website from DDoS attacks by mitigating them.
3. Increase redundancy and availability of content: Hardware failures (Team, 2019) and huge amounts of users creating traffic can hamper the normal functioning of a website. Due to the architecture and nature of the CDNs, they are more resilient to hardware failures and can handle very high traffic compared to the originating server.
4. Reduced website loading times: Through a technique (Buyya, Pathan, & Vakali, 2008) that relates to the geographical aspects of server positioning, the content that is delivered to users is close to them. This results in reduced loading times of websites resulting in a higher number of users accessing the web page and not giving up loading it. This rate is calculated statistically with a technique called bounce rate.

5. Reduced latency and packet loss: Data that is sent from one device to another over the internet is sent in packages. If these packages (Team, 2019) are sent over very long distances, there is a risk of encountering different failures such as package loss or package delay which can lead to packages not arriving in order (jitter). All this would create inconvenience for the end user and one solution could be to shorten the distance between the servers and the client using a CDN.

Figure 3.1: One single distribution server (left), and a system of CDN servers (right) (Team, 2019).

3.2.3 Proxy Servers

A proxy server is (Luotonen, 1998a) actually a portal between the user and the Internet, basically an intermediary between the two entities. When a user makes a request to a web page, it goes through the proxy server and then goes to the desired address, back through that proxy server again (in most cases) and then returns to the user, as stated in the following paper: (Luotonen, 1998b).

In the case of modern (Saini, 2011) proxy servers, they have a more varied role, for example acting as a web filter, firewall, caching information to improve speed and providing shared network connections. Proxy servers therefore become (Saini, 2011) a real protection and privacy mechanism for users who want to be protected from malicious software on the internet.

Other particular features (Luotonen, 1998b) of proxy servers are that they can change the IP address of the user sending the request (so that their exact location is not known), block access to certain pages and encrypt data in transit.

The main reasons for using proxy servers are the following:

1. Possibility to access locked resources: Under certain conditions (Sysel & Doležal, 2014) imposed by governments or private companies, the same proxy servers are used to block access to certain web pages. It is possible to use other proxy servers that allow access to restricted websites.
2. Monitoring and controlling the time children and employees spend on the Internet: In addition to the fact (Fabmi et al., 2001) that proxy servers can block access to certain pages entirely, they can count and monitor the time an individual spends on certain web pages and then report this to the entity/firm providing access to the Internet.
3. Increased speeds and saved bandwidth: Entities and organizations can have higher performance (Fabmi et al., 2001) if they use a proxy server, this is due to the technique and functionality of the proxy server to cache various web pages that can be sent to clients. That is, instead (Luotonen, 1998a) of having 50 local requests to a popular web page, if the proxy server has a recent version of the page it will send it back, and if not, the proxy server will make a single request to the page.

It is not enough just to mention the positive aspects of these technologies, the negative aspects of this technique must also be highlighted and listed.

1. Proxy servers without encryption: The risk (Luotonen, 1998b) these servers bring is that third parties can intercept data that is not encrypted, basically it's like sending an unsecured message, which can be done without a proxy server.

One last feature worth mentioning is the different types of proxy servers that exist, and they fall into various categories such as:

- Proxy with high anonymity: This type (Luotonen, 1998b) of proxy uses a technique whereby the IP address presented to the web server is periodically changed.
- Completely anonymous proxy: These proxy servers (Luotonen, 1998b) will be seen by the server receiving a request but will not reveal the identity of the user (IP), this technique helps to hide the user from location-based marketing campaigns.
- Transparent proxy: As the name implies, these proxies (Fabmi et al., 2001) will provide the IP of the end web server, these proxies are easy to set up and are used by public locations such as libraries because they are easy to set up.
- Distorting proxy: The novelty that these proxy servers (which are seen by the web host) come with, is that a fake IP is given to the user, this method (Fabmi et al., 2001) can avoid content restrictions in certain geographical areas.

3.3 DFINITY's importance in blockchain

DFINITY is a company (Hanke et al., 2018) that created a decentralized network design whose protocols generate a reliable virtual blockchain computer running on top of a peer-to-peer network upon which software can be installed and can operate in the tamper-proof mode of smart contracts. The goal (Hanke et al., 2018) is for the virtual computer to analyse computations quickly, to provide predictable performance, and for computational and storage capacity to scale up without bounds as demand for its services increases.

3.3.1 DFINITY'S consensus algorithm

Proof-of-useful-work is the solution offered by DFINITY, and it is more complex than other existing solutions. This procedure is used by node machines that don't actually deal with hashing, but simply produce (I. C. team, 2023l) and process various blocks containing transactions that represent smart contract computations. Node machines, must be built with specifications that are standard, this is because nodes do not compete with each other, but in fact are required to perform the same amount of computations. If a node deviates (I. C. team, 2023l) from the group quota, it can be punished.

3.4 Blockchain and the traditional internet services

Now that we've highlighted the various technologies that help make the internet work, we can see how different they are from blockchain.

In terms of use cases, its easy to see (Wiesflecker, 2020) that the purpose of the Internet differs massively from blockchain, though they share parallels when it comes to the manner in which their use cases and ecosystem develop. The Internet focuses (Wiesflecker, 2020) much more on information exchange, while blockchain focuses on value exchange. Blockchain will (Sharma, 2018) not work alone, it will work along with the internet. In the case of the Internet Computer, HTTPS outcalls will be used instead of the traditional oracles. The power of HTTPS outcalls (I. C. team, 2023i) on the Internet Computer lies in their ability to connect smart contracts directly to the Web 2.0 world, opening up a plethora of use cases. Retrieve market data from crypto exchanges, send emails, integrate with other blockchains, and more.

3.5 Conclusion

To wrap up this chapter, various key functionalities of blockchain have been explained and also listed a number of traditional web technologies that are currently in use (various types of hosting, proxies, CDNs). Afterwards the connection and link between classic web

technologies and the Internet Computer which aims to become the future of hosting the web has been examined. One example of the proposed transitions is from centralized platforms where one entity is the intermediary, to instead using smart contracts which are decentralised and do not need an intermediary but only participants. Novelty is also brought in with the Proof-of-useful-work consensus algorithm. It was also mentioned that the Internet Computer which based on Web 3.0 will still be able to communicate with the external Web 2.0 world (e.g. HTTPS calls from Internet Computer to the external web) as a result, it will not be a closed environment.

Chapter 4

Experimental Analysis of DFINITY

4.1 Description of the experimental setup

The main objective of this chapter is to explain, describe and expose the basic processes that the Internet Computer performs, through UML diagrams (activity, sequence, state and class). The four basic processes that will be analysed are: Peer-to-peer, consensus, message routing and execution. I will then move on to other functionalities such as canisters and NNS. Towards the end of the chapter there will be a transition to the program developed with Motoko and present the experimental results of the CRUD application and its features, off-chain and on-chain.

4.2 Implementation of the experimental procedures

We can better understand the implementation of the experimental procedures of DFINITY, by mapping architecture and processes of DFINITY. The core on which the Internet Computer is based, is made up of 4 important layers that form it, these are as follows:

1. Peer-to-peer
2. Consensus
3. Message routing
4. Execution

These layers are ordered in ascending order, the first being peer-to-peer and the last one being the execution layer (I. team, 2023b). I will attach UML diagrams of each of these layers on the following pages to go into more detail and better understand what processes are being run by Internet Computer.

Regarding the architecture of the consensus protocol layer, DFINITY has four levels as I previously mentioned, and when referring to the notary layer the following (I. team, 2023b) applies: A full Byzantine agreement protocol would be the only option. But instead of doing that, the DFINITY notary merely runs an optimistic protocol which achieves consensus under normal operation though may sometimes notarize more than one block per round (Hanke et al., 2018).

4.2.1 Peer-to-peer

The lowest protocol layer used by the Internet Computer is called Peer-to-Peer. This layer makes the information available from one Internet computer node, to reach other nodes in the same subnet efficiently.

As part of a replica architecture, the peer-to-peer (P2P) networking layer (Siffert, 2023) collects and advertises messages from users, from other nodes in its subnet blockchain, and from other subnet blockchains. Messages (Siffert, 2023) received by the peer-to-peer layer are replicated to all the nodes in the subnet to ensure the security, reliability, and resiliency.

The Internet Computer creates a secure network of messages (Harchol, 2023) (also called artifacts) through which we can communicate over the network. Artifacts are therefore considered to be the inputs to the canisters that host smart contracts. It is the P2P protocol that underlies the layers, and communicates directly with the consensus layer.

To better understand how peer-to-peer technology works, it is necessary to learn more about subnets. A subnet (I. C. team, 2023o) is a special kind of blockchain within the Internet Computer blockchain network that can seamlessly integrate with other blockchains to increase capacity. The Network Nervous System combines (I. C. team, 2023o) nodes from independent data centers to create subnets, which are used to host canister smart contracts. Each subnet runs its own blockchain, and canisters run on-chain in such a way that they can transparently call canisters on other subnets/chains.

Another good source is the developer documentation which states the following: Internet Computer subnet (Siffert, 2023) blockchains provide physical hardware and resources like CPU and memory for performing software operations. Each subnet is a blockchain that consists of some number of decentralized, independently owned and controlled machines connected peer computers called nodes that run the software components of the Internet Computer blockchain protocol.

The Internet Computer blockchain (Siffert, 2023) software components that run on each node are called a replica because they replicate state and computation across all the nodes in a subnet blockchain. The subnets are (I. C. team, 2023o) transparent to canister code and users of canisters, and direct interaction between subnets, and with subnets, is enabled by "Chain Keys,"

The gossip protocol plays an important role in the P2P layer, we need to highlight some of its features. A node in the subnet (I. C. team, 2023e) is connected with a subset of the

other nodes of the subnet its peers. Whenever a node receives an artifact from a peer or creates one itself as part of the IC protocol, it gossips this artifact to all its peers. By every node (I. C. team, 2023e) in the network doing exactly this, every artifact eventually propagates through the whole subnet, despite potential connectivity issues or malicious node behaviour.

In order to save bandwidth (I. C. team, 2023f), which would be wasted by sending an artifact to a peer that already has the artifact in its pool, the P2P layer does not send out artifacts immediately to all peers when requested by a client to broadcast an artifact. Instead, it creates (I. C. team, 2023f) a message called advert, which is a very small message with the hash of the artifact and some more metadata, and broadcasts this advert to all peers. Other peers (I. C. team, 2023f) then see the advert and decide whether they would like to download the corresponding artifact from that peer, and if so, they send an explicit request message to that peer, which will respond with the artifact itself.

The P2P (I. C. team, 2023e) layer allows the prioritization of artifacts such that the more crucial artifacts are broadcast throughout the subnet nodes more quickly than the others. Prioritizing some artifacts over others is important to ensure that the protocol can always make progress and not be starved of network bandwidth.

The figure 4.1 (New artifact in the artifact pool) refers to the process of adding an artifact to an artifact pool. The artifact is added locally, the gossip (I. C. team, 2023f) network creates a notice and sends it to all its peers in the overlay network. When (I. C. team, 2023f) a node receives an announcement from a peer, it is checked whether the artifact has already been downloaded or created by the node itself. If it hasn't, it adds it to the adverts queue of the peer that sent it.

If there is enough space (I. C. team, 2023f) in the unvalidated section of the artifact pool. We call the `download_next()` function to send the next artifact. Eventually we get the artifact with the highest priority and not the one we requested.

The second UML diagram, with the figure 4.2 and entitled 'The Download next functionality' is used (I. C. team, 2023f) to receive an artifact from a peer in the network.

The third UML diagram depicted in the figure 4.3 is titled "Receive Artifact" and highlights (I. C. team, 2023e) the processes and actions that are performed when operating the activity of receiving a requested artifact.

The figure number 4.4 (Transient network problems) represents (I. C. team, 2023f) a solution that is offered in case that there is a challenge with the connection in the network.

The fifth UML diagram, with the figure number 4.5 entitled "Disconnect, full queue" shows (I. C. team, 2021b) us the procedures followed if our node encounters various difficulties. That is, if it gets disconnected, or if its queue is full, and it runs out of space.

New Artifact in Artifact Pool

Figure 4.1: New artifact in the artifact pool

The "Download next" functionality

Figure 4.2: "Download next" functionality

How to receive an artifact?

Figure 4.3: How to receive an artifact?

Figure 4.4: Transient network problems

Disconnect, queue full

Figure 4.5: Disconnected or full queue

4.2.2 Consensus

The consensus protocol was entirely (I. team, 2023a) developed by the DFINITY team. The main role of this mechanism is to help a multitude of nodes, reach an agreement on which messages to process. Each subnet is based on blockchain and runs an instance of the Internet Computer, which in turn uses consensus. The main goal (I. team, 2023a) and objective of consensus is to make the nodes present in the subnets have the same block and ordered messages.

A cryptographic mechanism (I. team, 2023a) called random beacon is used to select one node (chosen at random) as the primary block maker (or leader) for the current round, the random beacon is also used if the primary block maker is faulty or the network is slow. The block makers for a round (I. team, 2023a) are chosen through a random permutation of the nodes of the subnet based on randomness derived from a random beacon.

The figure 4.8), titled "Random Beacon", is a random value shared next to the subnet's replicas, and is used to improve the consensus protocol.

As seen in figure 4.9), entitled "Notarization with Block Maker Ranking", it is possible to improve the capabilities of the notary. This technique involves the use of time thresholds which are divided into various stages. When a notary enters (I. C. team, 2021a) a round, it starts a timer. At the beginning of the timed period, it is only looking to create a notarization share for the block by the rank 0 block maker. Only (I. C. team, 2021a) if that fails after a certain amount of time does the notary fall back to a block proposal from the rank 1 block maker. After another preset amount of time, it will fall back even further to the rank 2 or rank 3 block maker. By having the notary take the block maker ranking into consideration, the goal is that we reduce the number of notarized blocks that we get every round.

Another important aspect (Team et al., 2022) that the Internet Computer incorporates is cryptographically guaranteed finality compared to the probabilistic finality offered by other blockchains. In the following, I will present several UML (activity) diagrams that exemplify the functionalities of the consensus mechanism within the Internet Computer.

In the first diagram with the figure 4.6, entitled "Block Making", I have outlined an essential step. In each round, a block maker (which is also a node) will propose a particular block to all nodes in the network. In the best case there will be only one block maker, but it is possible that in other cases there will be multiple block makers.

The second diagram, entitled "Notarization" (figure 4.7), illustrates the process of a block that wishes to be notarized. For this to happen, two-thirds of all nodes need to validate a block to allow its notarization.

Moving to the last diagram with the figure 4.10 entitled "Finalization process", I highlight the procedure that can observe agreement. This is made possible by a decoupled and asynchronous process for finalization, which helps us detect when agreement is reached. Notaries will create "finalization shares" on a block if that block has not notary-signed another block at the same height.

Block Maker

Figure 4.6: Block Making

Figure 4.7: Notarization

Figure 4.8: Random Beacon

Figure 4.9: Notarization with Block Maker Ranking

Finalization process

Figure 4.10: Finalization process

4.2.3 Message routing

Message routing is the third level in the stack of core technologies that make up the Internet Computer. The Internet Computer's blockchain has the ability to allow different

users to forward messages to the canisters that host smart contracts (team, 2023a), and for these canisters to communicate with each other. This component routes messages from all over the Internet Computer, reaching even the canisters found in other subnets of the blockchain. There are various functionalities that are considered as important and crucial to the Internet of Computing as the following (team, 2023a):

1. Certification of the state of the subnet.
2. Synchronize the state of the subnet with new or backlogged nodes.
3. Routing of messages between canisters that have occurred as a result of execution, within the same subnet or between different subnets.
4. Induction of messages into blocks after they have passed consensus.
5. Calling the executor layer after successful induction.

For the message routing, I decided to create three diagrams explaining the processes that I consider to be some of the most important.

The first diagram is entitled "High level intuition of a (Deterministic) Execution Cycle". The figure 4.11 describes (team, 2023a) the processes around the execution environment, which is informed about the states of the canisters but also manages and maintains them. The message routing procedure has the ability to insert messages into the input queues of the canisters, but can also remove messages from the output queues in order to successfully reroute them.

The second diagram (figure 4.12) entitled "How do messages reach other subnets" will help us understand how messages that are in a subnet-to-subnet flow can reach other subnets. The aspect covered is the procedure of inclusion of blocks, from the received flows from other subnets, into the receiving subnet.

The third and final diagram which is sequential (figure 4.13), entitled "Stream transfer protocol" is a concrete example of how two subnets can communicate in the stream transfer protocol.

High-Level Intuition of a (Deterministic) Execution Cycle

Xnet message transfer and inclusion in blocks

Figure 4.12: How do messages reach other subnets

Figure 4.13: Stream transfer protocol

4.2.4 Execution

The last and topmost layer is the execution layer. Its role is to schedule and execute messages that have been approved by consensus and inserted into the canister queues by the message routing. This being the procedure for changing the state of the subnet in a deterministic way for all existing nodes. It is necessary (team, 2023b) that the same sequence of messages is received by all nodes in the network. This procedure will help in such way that the final state of each node in the network will be the same, after the end of a round.

In the first diagram (figure 4.14) entitled "Scheduling canisters on the Internet Computer", I explain how it is possible to schedule canisters. The basis of this technique relies in a number (between 0 and 99) that is given to each canister depending on the resources it can provide to run the various tasks. This number is a form of representation for priority.

In the second figure 4.15 "Executing a single message". I explain in broad terms what happens when a message is in the queue of a canister, and is taken over by that canister's execution procedure.

In the third diagram with the figure 4.16, we have represented in a visual way how

subnets make progress within the Internet Computer. It is necessary to understand this concept because it is closely related to the fact that the Internet Computer is a network of canisters. Depending on the needs and how many more canisters are installed on the Internet Computer, the IC will create more subnets.

The principle of "Time Slicing" is particularly important (represented by figure 4.17) because it ensures that a canister that has been running for a long time will not block the system for too long.

Scheduling canisters on the IC

Number indicates in percentage approximately how much of a subnet's single compute core the canister has reserved.

Priority can be viewed as how many resources it has reserved on the IC.

Figure 4.14: Scheduling canisters on the Internet Computer

Executing a single message

Figure 4.15: Executing a single message

How do subnets make progress on the IC?

Figure 4.16: Subnets progress

Figure 4.17: Time slicing

4.3 Experimental results analysis and interpretation

In this section we will analyse how a sample application on DFINITY can be implemented and evaluated. There are a multitude of possibilities when it comes to deploying and launching an application.

In the figure 4.18 ("Creating a DFX project on the Internet Computer"), I show the steps required to create an empty, predefined project. The next necessary step is to launch it. The advantage of the command line execution environment provided by DFINITY, is that it is intuitive and that can be used easily. On average, with 2-3 commands and related parameters, an application can be launched locally.

4.3.1 Creating a dapp project locally via dfx

Figure 4.18: Creating a DFX project on the Internet Computer

In the figure 4.19 (Deploying a DFX project locally) I will highlight the same procedure for launching a dapp application, which is also done via the command line execution environment (dfx). The difference is that the on-chain implementation requires us to have a number of cycles at hand that are obtained by transforming ICP coins into cycles. This need arises because, the canisters consume a number of cycles depending on the operations that they perform.

Deploying a DFX project on-chain on the Internet Computer is shown in the figure 4.20. This is the initial and primary method for launching a web application or static page on the Internet Computer

The UML (figure 4.21) diagram (deploying a DFX project on-chain with Fleek.co) shows one of the newest procedures and most promising technique, by which a programmer can upload his static website. One of the current limitations of Fleek.co (Fleek.co, 2023) is that the platform can only create canisters that will contain static websites. So no back-end canisters will be created on Internet Computer.

What is the procedure for launching an application on the Internet Computer?

One of the first things I wanted to check and test is the release of the so-called canisters containing front-end and back-end code. I started doing this locally, we can see the different possible states and actions.

I will answer this question by displaying the necessary procedures in the form of UML (activity) diagrams on the following pages.

4.3.2 Deploying a project locally

Figure 4.19: Deploying a DFX project locally.

4.3.3 Deploying a project on-chain via CLI

Figure 4.20: Deploying a DFX project on-chain on the Internet Computer.

4.3.4 Deploying a project on-chain with Fleek.co

Figure 4.21: Deploying a DFX project on-chain on the Internet Computer with Fleek.co

Some of the other important operations (figure 4.22) are stopping or deleting canisters, these can be seen in more detail in the following diagram.

Stop or delete a canister

Figure 4.22: Start/Stop a canister

4.4 Features to be mentioned

The techniques mentioned in the previous section belong to the category of those that are considered essential. But in this section I want to talk about some other processes and features that are considered important for the proper functioning of the Internet Computer.

4.4.1 Canister lifecycle

On the Internet Computer (I. C. team, 2023d) smart contracts come in the form of canisters. These are computational units which bundle together code and state. Canisters expose endpoints which can be called both by other canisters and by parties external to the IC, such as browsers or mobile apps. A dapp (I. C. team, 2023c) built on the Internet Computer can be composed of one or more canisters. Some of the dapp's canisters may provide web interfaces that end-users can access through their browser. There are only (I. C. team, 2023n) two types of calls: non-committing query calls and committing update calls. The code (I. C. team, 2023d) of a canister consists of a WebAssembly (Wasm) module. The state consists of the usual heap of the Wasm module, together with stable memory, a special type of memory which plays an important role in the life-cycle of a canister.

Some important aspects (I. C. team, 2023c) of a canister:

1. They are general purpose, meaning that the class of smart contract programs is Turing complete.
2. They are tamperproof, meaning that the instructions of the program are carried out faithfully.
3. They're autonomous, meaning that a smart contract is executed automatically by the network.
4. They are composable, in that they may interact with one another, and support tokenization, meaning that they may use and trade digital tokens.

If we want to update a canister (figure 4.23), it is necessary to replace the Wasm module of a canister, but at the same time keep the data between the different versions. Basically, upgrades allow canisters to serialize and deserialize data between versions, which is saved in the stable memory.

Flow for upgrading (I. C. team, 2023b) a canister:

Upgrading a canister

In the figure 4.24, I pictured a state diagram (canister states), we can have several possible states. The canister at any time will be in any of the 3 states (running, stopping or stopped).

Canister possible states - system side

Figure 4.24: Canister states

- **Running** Requests and responses are processed normally.
- **Stopping** All the requests and processes, responses are rejected.
- **Stopped** All the requests are rejected.
- **Deleted** It is not explicitly a state, the canister will not be any more recorded on the platform.
- **Deallocated** Cycles account, canister ID and the controller are recorded; there are no reservations, call context and code that are active.
- **Frozen** It is possible to unfreeze from this state by adding cycles, otherwise it will reject all the requests.

4.4.2 Canister creation

In the figure 4.25 I want to highlight the process of creating a canister in relation to the Internet Computer's monetary policy. We can observe the steps and stages that are necessary to successfully launch a canister in a subnet. Similar steps are described in the next section, but these are more related to the programming side.

Canister creation using cycles

Figure 4.25: Canister creation

4.4.3 Network Nervous System

The open algorithmic framework (I. C. team, 2023k) that controls the Internet Computer blockchain is called the Network Nervous System (NNS). One of its most important improvements (I. C. team, 2023k) is its capability to add new node providers, add node machines to the blockchain network, and construct new subnet blockchains to expand capacity. It can also upgrade the Internet Computer protocol and software operating on node computers.

In the figure 4.26, we have as an example the proposal of a neuron to add another node to the subnetwork, and what are the procedures to carry out this proposal.

We need to understand that in order to have voting power, it is necessary to have a number of tokens locked in a neuron. These tokens (Team et al., 2022) are locked for a period of time, and give us the ability to vote on the various proposals of the other participants. If we don't want to vote on various proposals for different reasons, we can track certain neurons, also called "followees", this is depicted in the figure 4.28. The user's neuron will vote according to what the majority of the "followees" vote for. This method can be useful if a node holder has no knowledge of a proposal, since tracking some neurons can be done based on different topics.

Some of the topics into which neuron proposals can be classified are:

- ExchangeRate: Proposals on the real-time value of tokens.
- SubnetManagement: Changes to topology, nodes added or deleted from the subnet.
- NodeAdmin: Related to how the nodes are managed.
- NetworkEconomics: It pays attention to economic proposals, such as what rewards should be offered. This is portrayed in figure 4.27.

Neurons that are active due to their participation are rewarded. In order to avoid an excessive number of unnecessary proposals, a fee (paid by the proposing neuron) is applied to proposals that are rejected.

Submitting a node proposal

Figure 4.26: Submitting a node proposal

Figure 4.27: Voting rewards

Figure 4.28: Following

4.4.4 Contract execution on the blockchain in its structure

To encompass the multiple technologies and functionalities explained and outlined above, I used a class diagram 4.29, which helped in explaining the major pillars of the Internet Computer along with its operations and attributes. With this, I represented the NNS (Network Nervous System), the subnet, the nodes and the canisters that are hosted by the nodes. This type of depiction helps us to visualize more easily, the positioning of the canister in the Internet Computer's blockchain, which can be manoeuvred, controlled and accessed much more easily than other hierarchically superior components. It can be seen that the smart contracts are held at the canister level.

Contract execution on the blockchain

Figure 4.29: Contract execution on the blockchain

4.4.5 What is Motoko?

In this section I will give some details about Motoko, which is the programming language I used to develop the Smart Contract for my web application. The language called Motoko has been (Team et al., 2022) designed in such a way that is well aligned with the operational semantics of the IC. Motoko is (Team et al., 2022) a strongly typed, actor-based programming language with built-in support for orthogonal persistence and asynchronous message passing. Orthogonal persistence simply means that all memory maintained by a canister is automatically persisted (i.e., it does not have to be written to a file). It is important to define what actor-based means because it comes with a considerable number of advantages from which Motoko benefits. The Actor Model (Hewitt, 2010) is characterized by inherent concurrency of computation within and among Actors, dynamic creation of Actors, inclusion of Actor addresses in messages, and interaction only through direct asynchronous message passing with no restriction on message reception order. As a consequence, in the Actor

Model (Hewitt, 2016), there is no hypothesis of simultaneous change in multiple locations, as such there be no single point of failure can be an important aspect of security. Actions that the actor can perform concurrently when receiving a message are (Hewitt, 2016) : sending messages to (unforgeable) addresses of actors that it has, create new actors, designate how to handle the next message it receives

It's also important (support, 2023) to mention that the Internet Computer can support any number of different software frameworks such as the Rust (team, 2023c) programming language. The DFINITY Foundation is also working (support, 2023) on an SDK that support other languages such as C. The IC also provides (Team et al., 2022) a messaging interface definition language and wire format called Candid, for typed, high-level, and cross-language interoperability. This allows any two canisters, even if written in different high-level languages, to easily communicate with one another.

4.4.6 Experimental results of the Hierarchify chat app

Theoretical foundations of the application

The development of my application, appears as a direct response to the desire to understand the basic mechanisms necessary for a chat application to be hosted on the Internet Computer. One of the most fascinating features of this web application is that it does not use a traditional database (MySQL or NoSQL) but uses a Hash Map with various data structures. The Hash Map is stored in the stable memory of the Internet Computer.

Reasons for making the application

After lengthy consultations, discussions and ideas with my coordinating professor, together we agreed that I would develop multiple models and one project highlighting various features of the Internet Computer. I decided to explore the subject in more depth, in order to test new functionalities proposed by DFINITY's team.

Developed application

The proposed application concept is depicted in the figure 4.30, it is basically a platform with a simple chat interface. The user is greeted by various options: 1) He can enter a chat room by entering a special code or 2) He can generate his own room that has a special code assigned to it. This application was designed with the potential purpose of being used in case a company wants to have a hierarchical structure of dialogues between employees and bosses. So either the CEO of the firm creates a room with other subordinates, and these subordinates are in turn bosses to other lower ranked employees. I'll attach a figure that refers to the previously mentioned ideas.

Another important objective I focused on, was to create a diagram that could highlight the main use case. I decided that a good solution would be to use a sequence diagram that illustrates the interaction between the various objects and the operations that are performed on them, as well as the sequence of operations. I have depicted in the figure 4.31 the actions that take place when pressing the buttons to enter the chat room and when sending a message. I have emphasized among these, communication with the graphical interface but also requests sent to the smart contract such as: getting the list of messages along with different chat room data, or updating the list of messages.

Figure 4.30: Concept of a chat system based on hierarchy

Figure 4.31: Sequence diagram of chat functionalities

One of the most interesting technologies that can be considered the cornerstone of this application, is regarding the fact that the chat application does not use a database for anything. It uses various data structures that are stable and persisted in the canister. I will discuss this aspect in more detail in the following chapters.

To better test a sample application on the Internet Computer, I developed a sample application called "Hierarchify". This is intended to highlight the different possibilities and ways of working needed to bring the project to a successful completion.

This is a chat application that has 2 inputs:

1. The access code for the chat room.
2. The username.

As we can see in the figure 4.32, the registration or authentication is not required.

Enter the ChatRoom ID:

Name

Join Chat Room

Figure 4.32: Chat system based on hierarchy

The chat room ID can be set from a control panel as well as many other features that are not shown here.

Depending on the name of the person who created the room (as seen in figure 4.33), they are considered to be the chat room manager and will have a coloured badge displayed next to their name.

Figure 4.33: Inside the Chatroom

It was possible to highlight a clear hierarchy within a group/subgroup of a company. Each boss or higher-ranking person can create their own chat group. As a result, I will attach a class diagram that highlights all the operations that can be done within this application. I have worked to successfully integrate the 4 CRUD operations (create, read, update and delete). The figure with the number 4.34 represents a class diagram. It contains the functionalities of the class type "actor" that can be found in my code.

Hierarchify chat app class

Figure 4.34: DHierarchify actor class

A particularly important factor is the existence of `preupgrade()` and `postupgrade()` functions (DFinity, 2023). These functions make it possible to persistently save the variable "chatRooms" which is of type `HashMap` and is a more complex data type that is not by default stable.

4.5 On-chain project

The developed project can be viewed and examined in more detail at the following addresses:

1. Front-end canister <https://mywdq-5yaaa-aaaap-abc6q-cai.icp0.io>

2. Backend canister with Candid UI: <https://a4gq6-oaaaa-aaaab-qaa4q-cai.raw.ic0.app/?id=m7xfe-qaaaa-aaaap-abc6a-cai>
3. IC canister explorer IC Dashboard: <https://dashboard.internetcomputer.org/canister/m7xfe-qaaaa-aaaap-abc6a-cai>
4. IC canister explorer ICSCAN: <https://icscan.io/canister/m7xfe-qaaaa-aaaap-abc6a-cai>

Backend canisters come (I. C. team, 2023m) with a default user interface called Candid UI that will allow you to interact with the canister methods without writing any frontend code. It must be noted that before a chat room can be used, it must first be created. Also, the front-end canister will display content as long as it has cycles available, once it has run out of cycles the chat app will not work any more. Attached below are images capturing some of the web applications mentioned previously.

Figure 4.35: The front-end of Hierarchify on-chain

→ ↻ a4gq6-oaaaa-aaaab-qaa4q-cai.raw.ic0.app/?id=m7xfe-qaaaa-aaaap-abc6a-cai

Canister ID: [m7xfe-qaaaa-aaaap-abc6a-cai](#)

Candid UI

Browse and test your API with our visual web interface.

createChatRoom: (record {id:nat; creator:text; messages:vec record {id:nat; text:text;} → ())

id creator messages

deleteChatMessage: (nat, nat) → (text)

Figure 4.36: Candid UI, the backend of Hierarchify

Figure 4.37: The running canister and its ID, represented by the IC Dashboard

4.6 Conclusion

Concluding this chapter, it is considered that analysing the basic processes carried out by the Internet Computer helped in understanding the technical details of how it works. By building on this knowledge base, it was possible to develop a chat application using Motoko (explained in the subsection 4.4.5), JavaScript, HTML and CSS. The application was designed with the aim of allowing the hierarchization of different roles in the company and to create and enter chat rooms using a code and a username. It was possible to upload the application on-chain but also to see various data about the uploaded canister such as its ID, the subnet it belongs to or who controls it. There was an opportunity to successfully test the CRUD functionalities offered by the internet computer and compare the query and update methods.

Chapter 5

Evaluation

5.1 SWOT analysis of DFINITY's platform

The aim of this chapter is to give an overview of the Internet Computer. I will do this using a SWOT analysis that will list various strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. I will then move on to the roadmap given by the DFINITY team about future improvements, and will highlight some of the most promising ones.

I would like to explain why I think that it is necessary to use the SWOT analysis in my master thesis and what benefits it brings. Many (Merba, 2017), organizations carry out SWOT analysis at a strategic planning stage, try to identify and examine the existing resources, both internally and externally, investigating their trends and patterns that may have either positive or negative impacts to businesses. In other words, SWOT has been used by countless (Helms & Nixon, 2010) practitioners, marketing researchers, and is a frequent and popular tool for business marketing and strategy students. Its simplicity and catchy acronym (Helms & Nixon, 2010) perpetuates its usage in business and beyond as the tool is used to assess alternatives in complex decision situations.

One cause for the various failures in many projects started, is due to the lack of a SWOT analysis as we can see from the following research paper (Merba, 2017). Many organisations fail to achieve set goals within a given time period because they are unable to fix their business strategies and alignments. It is often the case (Merba, 2017) due to the organisations inability to properly implement the SWOT analysis models in business institutions.

SWOT analysis is not limited to scientific papers and can be extrapolated to many fields such as business environments. As a framework (Pickton & Wright, 1998), SWOT analysis is highly commended for its simplicity and value in focusing attention on key issues which affect business development and growth. It therefore has the potential to become a significant tool in identifying the factors which are most likely to influence a firm's strategy and success. Having identified (Dyson, 2004) these factors, strategies are developed which may build on the strengths, eliminate the weaknesses, exploit the opportunities or counter the threats.

The strengths (Dyson, 2004) and weaknesses are identified by an internal appraisal of the organisation and the opportunities and threats by an external appraisal.

This is the SWOT analysis that I conducted on the Internet Computer, there are various aspects about the Internet Computer that I would like to highlight:

5.1.1 Strengths

- One of the strengths is the particularly fast transactions that the blockchain can carry out. This is due to "Chain Key Technology", which is based (I. team, 2023b) on the fact that a blockchain has only one public key and this factor causes a reduction in the amount of data that is needed to verify transactions.

Speed is also given (Team et al., 2022) by the fact that there is a differentiation between the distinct calls that can be made to smart contracts. The query call (approx duration of 200 milliseconds) does not change the state of a node and is processed by only one node. Whereas the Update call (approx duration of 2 seconds) requires validation by all nodes offering that contract.

- Scalability makes the Internet Computer a versatile technology. This is because it has the ability to scale up/down the network with nodes that make up another subnetwork as needed.

5.1.2 Weaknesses

- Platform limits: Although the DFINITY team claims that Internet Computer can host applications with absolutely no limits, a platform the size of YouTube or Instagram is non-existent. The largest app at the time of writing the master thesis had around 175,000 users (DSCVR, <https://dscvr.one/>).
- Specialized hardware is needed, this is because the specific hardware that is used by the nodes is standardized. Not only that, but the standard (Pena, 2023) hardware, can only be traded with permission from the DFINITY team (this procedure is not decentralized at all).

5.1.3 Opportunities

- Integration with Bitcoin: The Internet Computer is already (I. C. team, 2023a) linked to the Bitcoin network at the protocol level. The smart contracts that the canisters have, can create Bitcoin (I. C. team, 2023g) addresses, as well as send and receive Bitcoins directly from the Bitcoin network. This could, for example, allow fundraisers to accept Bitcoins.

- Integration with Ethereum: this feature (I. C. team, 2023h) is still at the implementation stage. It has the ambitious plan to allow smart contracts to communicate on networks other than their own.

5.1.4 Threats

- ICP currency volatility: In May 2021, the value of the ICP currency decreased by 95%. That's a very high figure, even for the cryptocurrency market. This is due to the flaws of the shares and the way the coin was offered. Some crypto analysts (Livni & Sorkin, 2023) say that "a token dropping over 90 percent in the first month after launch is highly unusual for a project of this scale". This has left many investors on hold and spread negative rumours about the project.

5.2 Suggestions for further research and development

One of the best sources for getting informed of what's coming on the Internet Computer is the Internet Computer Roadmap (I. C. team, 2023j). Here we can see the various technologies that the DFINITY team is focusing its efforts and resources on. The general topics are: Core protocol (43% of resources), boundary (6% of resources), system utils and dApps (8% of resources), governance (12% of resources), developer experience (14% of resources), infrastructure and operations (17% of resources). Some very useful indicators that these categories display are the various stages of development they are in, i.e. upcoming, In progress or deployed.

The core protocol is the department in which the most investments are made. If we access this section (I. C. team, 2023j) we see that the integration with Bitcoin has already been launched, but that "HTTPS Outcalls from Canisters" is in beta. These HTTPS outcalls from canisters are worth watching, because historically, smart contracts did not have the ability to communicate with the outside world, and for this purpose oracles emerged. They are centralized and within reach of intermediaries. This can expose them to attacks and higher fees. So HTTPS calls from the canisters directly to the internet computer blockchain will allow communication with the Web 2.0 world.

Instead, a substantial enhancement (I. C. team, 2023j) is currently in the development stage, and this will allow subnets to hold over a hundred thousand canisters. This future upgrade will be done because a decrease in subnet performance has been observed when exceeding this limit.

Other (I. C. team, 2023j) functionalities that are promising and are in development at the time of writing this master paper:

- Composite queries: this will allow programmers to more easily develop calls that call other calls.

- HostOS SSH access: This functionality will provide increased security by giving nodes SSH access.
- Subnet Splitting: Each subnet is limited as to how many messages it can process and how much memory these canisters can hold. When the subnet becomes overloaded, the canisters no longer respond well enough to commands. This is where the idea of adding enough replicas to a subnet comes from, which will then be placed in two groups, and then splitting can occur. This will be quick because all the replicas have the state of the other canisters in the subnet.
- Canister Lifecycle Hooks: this will automate the method of feeding funds into the canisters, currently done manually by the developer.

5.3 Conclusion

Wrapping up this chapter, it was possible to find and identify a number of strengths (scalability), weaknesses (limited applications), opportunities (integration with Ethereum) and threats (currency volatility) of the Internet Computer. Regarding the future and potential of the Internet Computer, it is important to examine DFINITY team's past successes. This is a good way to observe the future potential of the Internet Computer. As it can be seen, many of the proposed goals have been achieved (I. C. team, 2023j). It can be noticed that the most amount of effort is being put into the core protocol, and some of the most promising (I. C. team, 2023j) features are: composite queries, subnet splitting and canister lifecycle hooks.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Outlook

6.1 Thesis main findings and contributions summary

I analysed, created diagrams and developed a chat system using the tools provided by the DFINITY team, as I found these steps necessary to better understand the technology studied. At the same time, I wanted to have a greater overview, and for this reason I used different types of diagrams: activity, class, state and sequence. Thanks to these, I was able to understand and highlight many of the processes that help the Internet Computer work. Another advantage that UML diagrams bring, is that they are particularly flexible and help various entities to better understand different procedures. Initially, I had an overview of the important processes, which later also helped me to better understand the Internet Computer. Ultimately this led to developing a decentralized chat application, which in turn came with challenges and insights into a new programming language (Motoko).

The application I developed is of type CRUD, and I was able to test with it, the "stable memory" of the canisters. It was a challenge to implement a data structure that met the needs of my application. This is because I could not rely on simple data types (which are by default stable) such as integers and strings but used classes containing HashMaps and Lists which are not considered as "stable" types by default but have to go through a conversion process.

6.2 Implications of blockchain and related technologies

Initially my focus was mainly on highlighting the traditional way of hosting web applications, and then exploring the new technique. However, following discussions with the coordinator of my Master's thesis, I came to the conclusion that it would be necessary to touch upon, discuss and outline the mechanisms underlying the Internet computer. For this reason I analysed the 4 layers that underlie the internet computer and created UML diagrams that helped me to understand the various procedures that the internet Computer is

following.

I can consider that I have not been able to find a technology directly comparable to Internet Computer that has major similarities. This is due to a multitude of factors that I have listed above, but to summarise this, we can look at Internet Computer as a completely new and revolutionary way of delivering blockchain-based web apps, web hosting, and smart contracts.

6.3 Applications and future research of the methodology

I will consider continuing working on this project, to enhance the mentioned functionalities in a PhD thesis at the University of Fribourg. My attention was drawn to the existing themes in the Master's programme at this university, namely: Knowledge Blockchains and the PhD School on Business Informatics.

References

- Alabdulwahhab, F. A. (2018). Web 3.0: the decentralized web blockchain networks and protocol innovation. In 2018 1st international conference on computer applications & information security (iccais) (pp. 1–4).
- Anderson, S., & Bedre-Defolie, Ö. (2022). Online trade platforms: Hosting, selling, or both? *International Journal of Industrial Organization*, 84, 102861.
- Andrews, R. (2003). *Research questions*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- aws.amazon. (2023, 5 27). What is decentralization in blockchain? Retrieved 2023-05-27, from <https://aws.amazon.com/blockchain/decentralization-in-blockchain>
- Balen, J., Vajak, D., & Salah, K. (2020). Comparative performance evaluation of popular virtual private servers. *Journal of Internet Technology*, 21(2), 343–356.
- Baskerville, R., Pries-Heje, J., & Venable, J. (2009). Soft design science methodology. In *Proceedings of the 4th international conference on design science research in information systems and technology* (pp. 1–11). Retrieved from https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/1555619.1555631?casa_token=8TdZ2nSxuQUAAAAA:XgQXKY8MSBBZYZpWD82B4ApqFkoYyrhxtvpc3q-ro05saV60oesY9_ZbG8pPmwjBA4-okVj1RA49PQ
- Bentov, I., Lee, C., Mizrahi, A., & Rosenfeld, M. (2014). Proof of activity: Extending bitcoin’s proof of work via proof of stake [extended abstract] y. *ACM SIGMETRICS Performance Evaluation Review*, 42(3), 34–37.
- Buyya, R., Pathan, M., & Vakali, A. (2008). *Content delivery networks* (Vol. 9). Springer Science & Business Media.
- Comellas, J. O. F., Presa, I. G., & Fernández, J. G. (2010). Sla-driven elastic cloud hosting provider. In 2010 18th euromicro conference on parallel, distributed and network-based processing (pp. 111–118).
- Day, J. D., & Zimmermann, H. (1983). The osi reference model. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 71(12), 1334–1340.
- Dfinity. (2023). Stable variables and upgrade methods. Retrieved 2023-03-04, from <https://internetcomputer.org/docs/current/motoko/main/upgrades#preupgrade-and-postupgrade-system-methods>
- Di Pierro, M. (2017). What is the blockchain? *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 19(5), 92–95.
- Dresch, A., Lacerda, D. P., Antunes Jr, J. A. V., Dresch, A., Lacerda, D. P., & Antunes, J. A. V. (2015). *Design science research*. Springer.
- Dyson, R. G. (2004). *Strategic development and swot analysis at the university of warwick*.

- European journal of operational research, 152(3), 631–640.
- El Faqir, Y., Arroyo, J., & Hassan, S. (2020). An overview of decentralized autonomous organizations on the blockchain. In Proceedings of the 16th international symposium on open collaboration (pp. 1–8).
- Fabmi, H., Latif, M., Sedigh-Ali, S., Ghafoor, A., Liu, P., & Hsu, L. (2001). Proxy servers for scalable interactive video support. *Computer*, 34(9), 54-60. doi: 10.1109/2.947092
- Fleek.co. (2023). To dfinity and beyond: Static front-end hosting, internet computer gateway, and the next steps. Retrieved 2023-03-08, from <https://blog.fleek.co/posts/to-dfinity-and-beyond-dfinity-frontend-hosting>
- Gralla, P. (1998). *How the internet works*. Que Publishing.
- Gupta, M. (2018). *Blockchain for dummies*. Retrieved from <https://www.ibm.com/downloads/cas/36KBMB0G>
- Hanke, T., Movahedi, M., & Williams, D. (2018). Dfinity technology overview series, consensus system. arXiv preprint arXiv:1805.04548. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.04548.pdf>
- Harchol, Y. (2023, 3 24). Peer-to-peer. Retrieved 2023-03-24, from <https://internetcomputer.org/how-it-works/peer-to-peer-p2p/>
- Helms, M. M., & Nixon, J. (2010). Exploring swot analysis—where are we now? a review of academic research from the last decade. *Journal of strategy and management*, 3(3), 215–251.
- Hevner, A., Chatterjee, S., Hevner, A., & Chatterjee, S. (2010). Design science research in information systems. *Design research in information systems: theory and practice*, 9–22.
- Hevner, A. R. (2007). A three cycle view of design science research. *Scandinavian journal of information systems*, 19(2), 4.
- Hewitt, C. (2010). Actor model of computation: scalable robust information systems. arXiv preprint arXiv:1008.1459.
- Hewitt, C. (2016). Actor model of computation for scalable robust information systems. HAL, 2016(0). Retrieved from <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=ac1f5418a733424a63d55967606e100db8cd8c42>
- IBM. (2023, 5 28). What are smart contracts on blockchain? Retrieved 2023-05-28, from <https://www.ibm.com/topics/smart-contracts>
- Kelly, T. (2020). Decentralized computing. *Queue*, 18(5), 41–53.
- Livni, E., & Sorkin, A. R. (2023, 4 19). Icp-cryptocurrency-crash. Retrieved 2023-04-19, from <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/06/28/business/dealbook/icp-cryptocurrency-crash.html>
- Luotonen, A. (1998a). *Web proxy servers*. Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Luotonen, A. (1998b). *Web proxy servers*. Prentice-Hall, Inc. Retrieved from <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.5555/275677>
- Mahmoud, M. S. (2011). *Decentralized systems with design constraints*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- March, S. T., & Storey, V. C. (2008). Design science in the information systems discipline: an introduction to the special issue on design science research. *MIS quarterly*, 725–730.
- Mathew, S., & Varia, J. (2014). Overview of amazon web services. *Amazon Whitepapers*, 105, 1–22.

- Merba, T. (2017). Swot analysis: A theoretical review emet gürel. *The Journal*, 10(51).
- Mingxiao, D., Xiaofeng, M., Zhe, Z., Xiangwei, W., & Qijun, C. (2017). A review on consensus algorithm of blockchain. In *2017 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)* (pp. 2567–2572).
- Mohanan, S., Parameswaran, N., et al. (2022). Finer criteria—what does it mean? *Cosmoderma*, 2.
- Molnar, D., & Schechter, S. E. (2010). Self hosting vs. cloud hosting: Accounting for the security impact of hosting in the cloud. In *Weis* (Vol. 2010, pp. 1–18).
- Monrat, A. A., Schelén, O., & Andersson, K. (2019). A survey of blockchain from the perspectives of applications, challenges, and opportunities. *IEEE Access*, 7, 117134–117151. Retrieved from <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&arnumber=8805074>
- Myllymäki, M. (2018). Development and evaluation study of a video-based blended education model. *JYU dissertations*(2).
- Nakamoto, S. (2008). Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system. *Decentralized business review*, 21260.
- Natarajan, H., Krause, S., & Gradstein, H. (2017). Distributed ledger technology and blockchain.
- Nofer, M., Gomber, P., Hinz, O., & Schiereck, D. (2017). Blockchain. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 59(3), 183–187.
- Papagianni, C., Leivadeas, A., & Papavassiliou, S. (2013). A cloud-oriented content delivery network paradigm: Modeling and assessment. *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, 10(5), 287–300. Retrieved from <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/6461891> doi: 10.1109/TDSC.2013.12
- Peppers, K., Tuunanen, T., Rothenberger, M. A., & Chatterjee, S. (2007). A design science research methodology for information systems research. *Journal of management information systems*, 24(3), 45–77. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.2753/MIS0742-1222240302>
- Pena, B. P. (2023, 05 17). How to become an internet computer node operator: Beginner’s guide. Retrieved 2023-05-17, from <https://www.coinhustle.com/how-to-become-node-operators>
- Peng, G. (2004a). Cdn: Content distribution network. arXiv preprint cs/0411069.
- Peng, G. (2004b). Cdn: Content distribution network. arXiv preprint cs/0411069.
- Pickton, D. W., & Wright, S. (1998). What’s swot in strategic analysis? *Strategic change*, 7(2), 101–109.
- Pollock, P. (2013). *Web hosting for dummies*. John Wiley & Sons. Retrieved from https://books.google.ch/books?hl=ro&lr=&id=1i4CriFGulUC&oi=fnd&pg=PT19&dq=Web+hosting&ots=0Hbd_MR02z&sig=-Bsyfq8b1vk0rTG4e897490VQXs&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Web%20hosting&f=false
- Saini, K. (2011). *Squid proxy server 3.1: beginner’s guide*. Packt Publishing Ltd.
- Sharma, T. K. (2018, 9 10). What are smart contracts on blockchain? Retrieved 2023-05-29, from <https://www.blockchain-council.org/blockchain/is-blockchain-comparable-new-internet/>
- Shrimali, B., & Patel, H. B. (2022). Blockchain state-of-the-art: architecture, use cases, consensus, challenges and opportunities. *Journal of King Saud University-Computer*

- and Information Sciences, 34(9), 6793–6807.
- Siffert, S. (2023, 5 30). Nodes and subnet blockchains. Retrieved 2023-05-30, from <https://internetcomputer.org/docs/current/concepts/nodes-subnets>
- Sriman, B., Kumar, S., & Prabakaran, S. (2020, 09). Blockchain technology: Consensus protocol proof of work and proof of stake. In (p. 395-406). doi: 10.1007/978-981-15-5566-4_34
- support, D. (2023, 6 6). What is motoko. Retrieved 2023-06-6, from <https://support.dfinity.org/hc/en-us/articles/360057132652-What-is-Motoko>
- Sysel, M., & Doležal, O. (2014). An educational http proxy server. *Procedia Engineering*, 69, 128–132.
- Taivalsaari, A., Mikkonen, T., Ingalls, D., & Palacz, K. (2008). Web browser as an application platform. In 2008 34th euromicro conference software engineering and advanced applications (pp. 293–302).
- Team, D., et al. (2022). The internet computer for geeks. *Cryptology ePrint Archive*. Retrieved from <https://eprint.iacr.org/2022/087.pdf>
- team, I. (2023a, 3 26). How consensus works. Retrieved 2023-03-26, from <https://internetcomputer.org/how-it-works/consensus/>
- team, I. (2023b, 3 25). How the internet computer works. Retrieved 2023-03-25, from <https://internetcomputer.org/how-it-works>
- team, I. C. (2021a, 5 17). Achieving consensus on the internet computer. Retrieved 2023-05-31, from <https://medium.com/dfinity/achieving-consensus-on-the-internet-computer-ee9fbfbafcbc>
- team, I. C. (2021b, 7 13). Inside the internet computer | peer-to-peer (p2p). Retrieved 2023-05-31, from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HOQb01KIy9I>
- team, I. C. (2023a, 4 19). bitcoin-integration. Retrieved 2023-04-19, from <https://internetcomputer.org/bitcoin-integration>
- team, I. C. (2023b, 3 30). Canister lifecycle. Retrieved 2023-03-30, from <https://internetcomputer.org/how-it-works/canister-lifecycle/>
- team, I. C. (2023c, 6 1). Canister smart contract. Retrieved 2023-06-1, from https://wiki.internetcomputer.org/wiki/Canister_smart_contract
- team, I. C. (2023d, 6 1). Canister smart contracts. Retrieved 2023-06-1, from <https://internetcomputer.org/how-it-works/canister-lifecycle/>
- team, I. C. (2023e, 3 30). How it works: Peer-to-peer. Retrieved 2023-05-30, from <https://internetcomputer.org/how-it-works/peer-to-peer-p2p/>
- team, I. C. (2023f, 5 31). How it works: Peer-to-peer. Retrieved 2023-05-31, from [https://wiki.internetcomputer.org/wiki/IC_P2P_\(peer_to_peer\)_layer](https://wiki.internetcomputer.org/wiki/IC_P2P_(peer_to_peer)_layer)
- team, I. C. (2023g, 5 19). Ic bitcoin integration. Retrieved 2023-04-20, from <https://internetcomputer.org/docs/current/developer-docs/integrations/bitcoin>
- team, I. C. (2023h, 5 19). Ic ethereum integration. Retrieved 2023-04-20, from <https://internetcomputer.org/ethereum-integration>
- team, I. C. (2023i, 5 29). Ic https outcalls. Retrieved 2023-04-20, from <https://internetcomputer.org/https-outcalls>
- team, I. C. (2023j, 4 20). Ic-roadmap. Retrieved 2023-04-20, from <https://internetcomputer.org/roadmap>

- team, I. C. (2023k, 4 03). Network nervous system. Retrieved 2023-04-03, from <https://internetcomputer.org/how-it-works/network-nervous-system-nns>
- team, I. C. (2023l, 4 15). Proof-of-useful-work. Retrieved 2023-04-15, from https://wiki.internetcomputer.org/wiki/Proof_of_Useful_Work
- team, I. C. (2023m, 5 30). Smart contracts as a backend. Retrieved 2023-06-10, from https://internetcomputer.org/docs/current/tutorials/create_your_first_app/backend-overview
- team, I. C. (2023n, 4 1). What are canister smart contracts? Retrieved 2023-06-1, from <https://support.dfinity.org/hc/en-us/articles/360057605571-What-are-canister-smart-contracts->
- team, I. C. (2023o, 3 29). What is a subnet? Retrieved 2023-05-30, from <https://support.dfinity.org/hc/en-us/articles/360057132512>
- Team, S. S. (2019, 4 11). What is a cdn and how can i get one. Retrieved 2023-04-11, from <https://www.ssl.com/article/what-is-a-cdn-and-how-can-i-get-one-from-ssl-com/>
- team, T. I. C. (2023a, 3 27). How message routing works. Retrieved 2023-03-27, from <https://internetcomputer.org/how-it-works/message-routing/>
- team, T. I. C. (2023b, 3 29). How the execution layer works. Retrieved 2023-03-29, from <https://internetcomputer.org/how-it-works/execution-layer/>
- team, T. I. C. (2023c, 6 9). Introduction to developing canisters in rust. Retrieved 2023-06-9, from <https://internetcomputer.org/docs/current/developer-docs/backend/rust/>
- Thabane, L., Thomas, T., Ye, C., & Paul, J. (2009). Posing the research question: not so simple. *Canadian Journal of Anesthesia/Journal canadien d'anesthésie*, 56(1), 71–79.
- Urgaonkar, B., Shenoy, P., & Roscoe, T. (2002). Resource overbooking and application profiling in shared hosting platforms. In 5th symposium on operating systems design and implementation (osdi 02).
- Vashchuk, O., & Shuwar, R. (2018). Pros and cons of consensus algorithm proof of stake. difference in the network safety in proof of work and proof of stake. *Electronics and Information Technologies*, 9(9), 106–112.
- Venable, J., Pries-Heje, J., & Baskerville, R. (2016). Feds: a framework for evaluation in design science research. *European journal of information systems*, 25, 77–89.
- Vukolic, M., et al. (2021). On the future of decentralized computing. *Bulletin of EATCS*, 135(3). Retrieved from <https://vukolic.com/on-the-future-of-decentralized-computing.pdf>
- Vyawahare, H. (2021, 04). Blockchain technology: A brief overview. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology*, 755-758. doi: 10.48175/IJAR SCT-950
- White, P. (2017). *Developing research questions*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Wiesflecker, L. (2020, 4 30). What are smart contracts on blockchain? Retrieved 2023-05-29, from <https://medium.datadriveninvestor.com/comparison-of-blockchain-verus-the-internet-fad9cdc32487>
- Wu, J. (1998). *Distributed system design*. CRC press.
- Zhang, C., Wu, C., & Wang, X. (2020). Overview of blockchain consensus mechanism. In *Proceedings of the 2020 2nd international conference on big data engineering* (pp.

7–12).

- Zheng, Z., Xie, S., Dai, H.-N., Chen, W., Chen, X., Weng, J., & Imran, M. (2020). An overview on smart contracts: Challenges, advances and platforms. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 105, 475–491.
- Zimmermann, H. (1980). Osi reference model-the iso model of architecture for open systems interconnection. *IEEE Transactions on communications*, 28(4), 425–432.
- Zou, W., Lo, D., Kochhar, P. S., Le, X.-B. D., Xia, X., Feng, Y., . . . Xu, B. (2019). Smart contract development: Challenges and opportunities. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, 47(10), 2084–2106.